

**SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF EFFECTIVE
MANAGEMENT OF A GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTION**

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After our glorious homeland gained independence, unprecedented changes took place in the system of continuing education, as in all spheres. Continuing education is a holistic educational system consisting of logically interconnected and mutually reinforcing stages, developing from simple to complex, one of its main components is the school. As the main component of the continuous education system, the school today has the main task of educating and educating students, the future of our country, in accordance with current state educational standards, and realizing the constitutional right of the individual to education.

Currently, the direct management of the educational process and daily activities of the school is considered the official duty of the school principal, who, within the scope of his authority, performs such important tasks as organizing educational work at the school, ensuring the administrative, economic, and financial work of the school, creating a procedure for observing safety standards and rules at the school, and monitoring their work. Therefore, in the current era of social development, educational institutions should be staffed not by leaders who blindly follow the instructions of higher organizations, but by leaders who have a creative approach to each task in their activities, are aware of new thinking and modern management sciences, and also have excellent personal and professional qualities and managerial skills.

The management and administration of the general secondary education system as a component of social governance is one of the pressing issues of today. Therefore, in recent years, the government of our country has given a number of tasks to leading representatives of the industry and scientists to develop and implement mechanisms to increase the management efficiency of the continuing education system and improve the competence of management personnel. Over the past years, a lot of scientific research has been conducted in this field, which can be clearly seen in the scientific research work carried out by B.A.Abdullayev, Sh.Kh.Abdullayeva, D.S.Abdullajanova, K.S.Aliyeva, N.Boymurodov, E.S.Yoziev, X.A.Kadirova, N.T.Kariyeva, V.M.Karimova, I.I.Makhmudov, A.M.Makhmudov, D.G.Mukhamedova, A.S.Nazarov,

N.A.Ruzikulov, E.N.Sattarov, O.R.Shamiyeva, A.M.Shonazarov, O.E.Hayitov, E.G.Goziev and others.

A.M.Shonazarov's research found that "among the components of socio-psychological competence that are taken into account when appointing school principals, the cognitive and social components are of a priority nature, that the socio-psychological competence of a leader is most often manifested in the ability to influence a person in interpersonal relationships, and that most of the factors that prevent the manifestation of the level of socio-psychological competence of leaders are explained by external influences. The scientific conclusion is that in developing the socio-psychological competence of leaders working in the education system, a comprehensive and continuous approach based on psychotechnologies to the development of its affective, reflexive, and socio-cognitive components is effective" [3; 152].

In her research work conducted by M.Kh. Baybayeva with the aim of "developing proposals and recommendations for improving the mechanisms for creating a healthy and creative environment in the management activities of the head of an educational institution", it was expressed as a scientific innovation that "... the model for creating a healthy and creative environment in the management activities of the head of a secondary educational institution was improved through a strategic diagnosis of the trajectories of meaningful, diagnostic, communicative and design organizational activities, through the sustainable adaptation of the capabilities of individual-psychological, pedagogical conditions in working with employees to the level of productivity; through the integration of situational educational identity with acmeological activity in accordance with the principles of imprinting the mechanisms for creating a healthy and creative environment in the management activities of the head of a secondary educational institution in accordance with the anthropological and autopsychological characteristics of the head of a secondary educational institution" [1; 27].

In our scientific research, we tried to study the socio-psychological factors of the direct impact of the management style of the head of a general secondary educational institution, the predominant form of management in the school, the activities of methodological associations serving to guarantee the quality of education and its management, and the position occupied by deputy directors on the general indicators of school activity. For this, respondents were addressed with questions 11, 12, 13 of the special IPS, and the main attention was paid to the manifestation of management styles in real life in all three levels of

management personnel and their direct preservation in activity. As a result, it was possible to identify the preferred management form, exemplary methodological association, and the average level of deputy directors in need of reform (see Table 1).

Table 1
Responses given by respondents to questions related to IPS's "School Activities" (n=543)

	Indicators related to school activities	Min.	Mak.	Average	Standard deviation
1	Authoritarian	1	57	27,88	5,24
2	Democratic	13	56	31,95	4,51
3	Liberal	8	55	32,01	4,48
4	Exact sciences	12	58	26,96	5,49
5	Natural sciences	10	66	31,07	4,77
6	Social Studies	18	64	34,09	4,29
7	Coursework is optional	11	64	36,51	4,17
8	Deputy for Spiritual and Educational Affairs	5	68	27,09	5,12
9	Deputy for Economic Affairs	0	66	30,67	5,01

Our test takers showed the following criteria on the scales in question 11: "How do you perceive the form of management in the educational institution you work in?": "authoritarian" (27.88); "democratic" (31.95); "liberal" (32.01). In question 12: "Which of the methodological associations in the educational institution you work in do you consider satisfactory?": "exact sciences" (26.96); "natural sciences" (31.07); "social sciences" (34.09), in question 13: "Which of the deputy directors in the educational institution you work in do you consider to be in need of improvement?": "deputy director for academic affairs" (36.51); The standard was also determined for the scales "deputy for spiritual and educational work" (27.09) and "deputy for economic work" (30.67). This means the average of the minimum and maximum selection indicators, i.e., closeness to real life, the impartiality of the data provided by the test takers, and the accuracy of the primary statistical data (see Table 1).

Indeed, in order for the head of an educational institution to have a high reputation, it is advisable for him to set an example for his team members in all aspects and manage the team using an effective management style. In this regard, humanism, patriotism, national pride, internationalism, justice, conscientiousness, impartiality, empathy, sincerity, humility, honesty, purity,

responsibility, self-control, respect for others, demandingness of oneself and others, and a sense of humor are important qualities of leadership ethics. If these qualities lose their value in the leader and subordinates find out about this, they lose respect for this leader. At such times, some leaders try to intimidate employees, make unfair demands on them, humiliate them, and use other artificial methods to restore their reputation among the team. But these methods have never been proven to be effective. Since this is the case, it is advisable for a leader to study himself deeply, analyze his achievements and shortcomings, compare himself with others, and strive to master their positive aspects.

In the activities of the head of an educational institution, it is important to establish a healthy psychological environment in the work team. In this, the presence of communicative and oratorical abilities in the head plays an important role. In fact, since the basis of the management activity of the head is joint work with people and the process of communication between them, it is advisable that it be organized in a sincere and friendly spirit, based on a mutually positive psychological environment and support. This requires a leader to have high knowledge and experience, to study employees, to involve them in the training process based on their abilities and knowledge levels, to assign them to positions and tasks, to be able to notice their unique qualities, achievements and shortcomings, to be able to use their achievements, to eliminate their shortcomings, to be able to make full use of the employees' potential. After all, leadership is also a skill. If a person is knowledgeable but does not have the inherent ability to lead, he cannot lead the team, on the contrary, he will certainly lead the team to a dead end.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, rahbarlik murakkab kasb bo'lib, u shaxsdan nafaqat oliy ma'lumotga ega bo'lishni, balki maxsus bilim, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, hayotiy tajriba va malakalarga hamda zamon bilan hamnafas bo'lishni talab etadi. Bizning fikrimizcha, bugungi kunda zamonaviy ta'lim muassasasi rahbari shaxsida quyidagi muhim sifat va fazilatlarning bo'lishligi ayni muddaodir:

- 1) be politically mature, intellectually and spiritually mature, well-educated, and deeply thoughtful;
- 2) possess the knowledge, skills, and experience necessary for a leadership position, management principles, methods, and sufficient knowledge and skills in all aspects of the position held;

3) rationally organize the activities of subordinates in the team, demonstrate responsibility, accountability, conscientiousness, kindness, dedication, and a sense of duty in this process;

4) be morally pure and well-mannered, honest and fair, sincere and humble, highly demanding of oneself and others, responsible and selfless;

5) Possessing important qualities such as word and deed unity, diligence and efficiency, psychological selectivity, social motivation, critical thinking, organization, courage, entrepreneurship, business acumen, etc.

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